

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part VII

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2-Hydroxy-5-allyloxyacetophenone (Ia), on Claisen condensation with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium yielded 2-hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-6-allyloxychromone (IIa), which on dehydration and Claisen rearrangement gave 5-allyl-6-hydroxychromone (IVb). Cyclization of (IVb) with conc. sulphuric acid afforded 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (Va). This on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished 2-methyl-4H-furo(3, 2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIa). 4H-Furo (3, 2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIb) was synthesised from (IVb) by carrying out oxidation with osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate, followed by cyclization with PPA. Similarly, 2,9-dimethyl-4H-furo (3,2-f)-benzopyran-4-one (VIc) and 9-methyl-4H-furo (3, 2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VI d) were synthesised from 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-allyloxyacetophenone (Ic). (Ic) was prepared from 2,5-dihydroxytoluene through acetylation and Fries migration.

IN continuation of our work¹ we report here the synthesis of four new furochromones, viz. 2-methyl-4H-furo(3,2-f)benzopyran-4-one (VIa), 4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIb), 2, 9-dimethyl-4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIc) and 9-methyl-4H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VI d).

Claisen condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-allyloxyacetophenone (Ia)², with ethyl formate in the presence of pulverized sodium, gave 2-hydroxy-2, 3-dihydro-6-allyloxychromone (IIa). It gave pale red brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride after one minute. IR spectra: 3250 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1645 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$: 224 nm (log e 4.67), 339 (3.94); (MeOH + NaOH), 228 (4.63), 338 (4.28). It was dehydrated to corresponding chromone derivative (IVa), by using aqueous sulphuric acid. Claisen rearrangement of (IVa) gave 5-allyl-6-hydroxychromone (IVb), which on trituration with conc. sulphuric acid yielded 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-furo(3, 2-f)benzopyran-4-one (Va). The structure of which was confirmed by NMR: δ , 1.46, doublet, 3H, $J=7\text{Hz}$, CH_3 group at C_2-CH_3 ; 3.12-3.98, multiplet, 2H, two methylene protons at C_3-H_2 ; 4.86-5.11, multiplet, 1H, methine proton at C_2-H ; 6.11 doublet, 1H, $J=7\text{Hz}$, C_6-H ; 6.91, doublet, 1H, $J=9\text{Hz}$, C_9-H , 7.12 doublet, 1H, $J=9\text{Hz}$, C_8-H , 7.61, doublet, 1H, $J=7\text{Hz}$, C_5-H . This spectral data confirmed that the Claisen rearrangement of 6-allyloxychromone (IVa) took place at five position, and not at seven position; in the latter case, spectrum of cyclized product would have shown two singlets in the aromatic region instead of two doublets, each for one aromatic proton. Dehydrogenation of (Va) was done with palladised charcoal in boiling diphenyl ether to yield 2-methyl-4H-furo(3,2-f)-benzopyran-4-one (VIa).

The compound (IVb), on treatment with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate in ethyl acetate, followed by cyclization of 5-acetaldehyde product with polyphosphoric acid gave 4H-furo-(3,2-f)benzopyran-4-one (VIb).

2,5-Dihydroxytoluene when treated with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave an ester 2,5-diacetoxytoluene. The ester on Fries migration by using anhydrous aluminium chloride, converted 2,5-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (Ib). The structure of (Ib) was confirmed on the basis of NMR spectrum obtained for the compounds (IIb) and (IVb). The ketone (Ib), was subjected to allylation with allyl bromide and anhydrous potassium carbonate to give 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-allyloxyacetophenone (Ic), which on Claisen condensation with ethyl formate in presence of pulverized sodium yielded 2-hydroxy-2, 3-dihydro-6-allyloxy-7-methylchromone (IIb). IR spectra: 3:80 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1660 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); NMR (DMSO- d_6), δ , 2.23 singlet, 3H, CH_3 group at C_7-CH_3 ; 2.67-2.93 multiplet, 2H, two methylene protons at C_3-H_2 ; 4.54, doublet, 2H, $J=6\text{Hz}$, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$; 5.17-5.55, multiplet, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$; 5.75, triplet, 1H, at C_2-H ; 5.85-6.24, multiplet 1H, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$; 6.88, singlet, 1H, C_9-H ; 7.14, singlet, 1H, C_8-H ; This spectral data confirmed the cyclic structure (IIb) and not the ring open structure 3-(2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-allyloxy-phenyl)-3-oxopropanal (III). Besides this, there are two singlets in the aromatic region, which confirmed the ketone structure of (Ib).

The compound (IIb), on dehydration, followed by Claisen rearrangement and cyclization with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2,9-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-furo (3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (Vb). Dehydrogenation of (Vb) by palladised charcoal (10%) furnished 2,9-dimethyl-4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIc).

The reaction of (IVa), with osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate in ethyl acetate followed by cyclization with PPA, yielded 9-methyl-4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VI d). The NMR spectra for the compounds (VIa, b, c and d) are given after the experimental procedure of each.

- (Ia) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = H$
 (Ib) $R = H$, $R_1 = CH_3$
 (Ic) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = CH_3$

- (IIa) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = H$
 (IIb) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = CH_3$

- (III) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = CH_3$

- (IVa) $R = R_2 = H$, $R_1 = -CH_2CH=CH_2$
 (IVb) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = R_2 = H$
 (IVc) $R = H$, $R_1 = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_2 = CH_3$
 (IVd) $R = -CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$

- (Va) $R = CH_3$, $R_1 = H$
 (Vb) $R = R_1 = CH_3$

- (VIa) $R = CH_3$, $R_1 = H$
 (VIb) $R = R_1 = H$
 (VIc) $R = R_1 = CH_3$
 (VID) $R = H$, $R_1 = CH_3$

Experimental

Unless otherwise stated NMR spectra were taken in $CDCl_3$ solution on a 90 MHz spectrometer with TMS at an internal standard. The IR spectra (nujol) were determined with Perkin-Elmer 457 grating spectrophotometer. The UV spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer.

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-6-allyloxychromone (IIa) :

Pulverized sodium (1.15 g) was kept in dry ether (5 ml) in a flask fitted with water condenser and maintained with stirring at 20° for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. During this time the solution of 2-hydroxy-5-allyloxyacetophenone^a (1.92 g) in ethyl formate (16 ml) was added drop by drop as to react with sodium. When the reaction had subsided, more ethyl formate (8 ml) was

added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed at 65° for 10 minutes. It was then left for two days. Alcohol and water were successively added with care and the resulting alkaline solution was extracted twice with ether. The aqueous alkaline layer was acidified with cold dilute acetic acid. A crystalline brown solid separated slowly was filtered and washed with water. It crystallised from benzene as colourless small prisms, m.p. 114° , yield 1.2 g. After one minute it gave red-brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and colour became more fast on standing. (Found : C, 65.43 ; H, 5.41 ; $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.45 ; H, 5.45%).

6-Allyloxychromone (IVa) :

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-6-allyloxychromone (2 g) was taken with dilute sulphuric acid (30%, 60 ml) in a flask and heated on water bath for 2 hr. After cooling, the pasty product was separated, washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution, and purified by passing it over a column of active basic alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) as eluent. It crystallised as pale yellow needles from petroleum ether, m.p. 64° , yield 1.3 g. (Found : C, 71.78 ; H, 5.11 ; $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28 ; H, 4.95%).

5-Allyl-6-hydroxychromone (IVb) :

6-Allyloxychromone (1 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (6 ml) for 80 minutes ; after cooling the reaction mixture was poured into ice containing hydrochloric acid (20 ml). The separated product was treated with sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The product was chromatographed on silica gel, using benzene chloroform (4:1) mixture as an eluent. It crystallized as colourless shining thick needles from benzene, m.p. 186° , yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 71.15 ; H, 4.71 ; $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28 ; H, 4.95%). IR spectra : 3180 cm^{-1} (OH), 1635 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-furo(3,2-f)benzopyran-4-one (Va) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxychromone (0.6 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid (85%, 6 ml) in a water bath for 12 minutes, the contents was poured into crushed ice, the separated product was filtered and washed with dil. sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallized from petroleum ether as cream coloured needles, m.p. $123-24^\circ$, yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 71.76 ; H, 5.40 $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$; requires C, 71.28 ; H, 4.95%).

2-Methyl-4H-furo(3,2-f)benzopyran-4-one (VIa) :

A mixture of 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-furo(3,2-f)-benzopyran-4-one (0.3 g), palladised charcoal (10%, 0.5 g) and diphenyl ether (5 ml) was refluxed for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate steam distilled to remove diphenyl ether. The remaining residue was extracted with ethyl acetate, evaporated and chromatographed on silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (7:3) gave the product (0.16 g). It crystallized from ethanol as colourless small needles, m.p. 134° . (Found : C, 71.97 ; H, 4.50 ; $C_{12}H_8O_3$

requires C, 72.00; H, 4.00%). UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 227 nm (log e 4.64), 265 nm (log e 4.28), 294 nm (log e 4.28), 328 nm (log e 4.31); NMR, δ , 2.53 (s, 3H, C₂-CH₃), 6.33 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C₅-H), 7.22 (d, 1H, J=9Hz, C₆-H), 7.42 (s, 1H, C₃-H), 7.65 (d, 1H, J=9Hz, C₈-H), 7.85 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C₆-H).

4*H*-furo(3,2-*f*) benzopyran-4-one (VIb) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxychromone (0.6 g) in ethyl acetate (80 ml) and osmium tetroxide (60 mg) in water (30 ml) were vigorously stirred for 15 minutes. Potassium periodate (1.5 g) was added in small quantities to the dark solution over a period of 2 hr. The reaction mixture was stirred 1 hr more. The ethyl acetate layer was separated, washed with water and dried with sodium sulphate and distilled. The residue, 5-acetaldehyde product was taken in PPA (12 ml) and heated in an oil bath for 1 1/2 hr at 115°. It was then poured over ice. The separated solid was extracted with ethyl acetate, washed successively with very dil. sodium hydroxide solution and water, dried with sodium sulphate and the solvent distilled off. The crude product was dissolved in benzene (1.5 ml) and percolated through a column of silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (2:3) yielded VIb (0.14 g), which crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 188° (Found : C, 70.49; H, 3.32, C₁₁H₆O₃ requires C, 70.98; H, 3.23 %). UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 262 nm (log e 4.22), 291 nm (log e 4.26), 318 nm (log e 4.27); NMR: δ , 6.38 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C₅-H), 7.29 (d, 1H, J=2Hz, C₈-H), 7.35 (d, 1H, J=9Hz, C₆-H), 7.7-7.9 (m, 3H, C₂-H, C₆-H and C₈-H).

2,5-Dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (Ib) :

2,5-Diacetyltoluene m.p. 49-50° (4.16 g) prepared from 2,5-dihydroxytoluene by the action of acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine, was thoroughly mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.0 g) and the mixture slowly heated in an oil bath at 100° for 1 hr and then at 120° for 1 1/2 hr more. The solid contents were poured into a beaker containing crushed ice (200 g) and conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml) when the solid product separated out, was filtered and washed with water, dissolved in (8%) sodium hydroxide solution. The filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave 2,5-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (1.8 g). It was crystallized from aqueous ethanol, m. p. 148-49°. (Found : C, 65.50; H, 5.74; C₉H₁₀O₃ requires C, 65.06; H, 6.02%). IR: 3110 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1645 (>C=O).

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-allyloxyacetophenone (Ic) :

A mixture of 2,5-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (3.32 g), anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g) and allyl bromide (1.8 ml) in dry acetone (80 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8 hr. After the evaporation of acetone the remaining solution was acidified by dil. hydrochloric acid, and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was shaken with 12% sodium hydroxide solution and the separated sodium salt was filtered.

It was then acidified and extracted with ether. On evaporation of ether greenish yellow colour liquid was obtained which was used for further reaction.

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-6-allyloxy-7-methylchromone (IIb) :

The solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-allyloxyacetophenone (3.0 g) in ethyl formate (16 ml) was allowed to react slowly with pulverized sodium (1.72 g) kept in dry ether (5 ml) at 15° for 1 hr. More ethyl formate (9 ml) was added as usual, and the reaction mixture was refluxed in a water at 55° for 15 minutes and left overnight. It crystallised from aqueous ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 142° (decom.), yield 1.7 g. It did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride even on keeping for long time. (Found : C, 67.08; H, 5.98; C₁₃H₁₄O₄ requires C, 66.67; H, 5.98%). UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 228 nm (log e 4.80), 324 nm (log e 4.22); (MeOH + NaOH) 227 nm (log e 4.37); 324 nm (log e 4.20).

6-Allyloxy-7-methylchromone (IVc) :

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-6-allyloxy-7-methylchromone (1.8 g) was dehydrated by using dilute sulphuric acid (30%, 50 ml) in a water bath for 90 minutes. It crystallised as colourless shining needles, m.p. 80-82°, yield 1.1 g. (Found : C, 72.11; H, 5.62; C₁₃H₁₂O₃ requires C, 72.21; H, 5.55%). NMR: δ , 2.33 (s, 3H, C₇-CH₃), 4.58 (d, 2H, J=6Hz, -OCH₂CH=CH₂), 5.17-5.49 (m, 2H, -OCH₂CH=CH₂), 5.81-6.14 (m, 1H, -OCH₂CH=CH₂), 6.20 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C₃-H), 7.14 (s, 1H, C₈-H), 7.38 (s, 1H, C₆-H) 7.67 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C₂-H).

5-Allyl 6-hydroxy-7-methylchromone (IVd) :

5-Allyloxy-7-methylchromone (1.5 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (12 ml) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The separated product was crystallised from benzene- as white plates, m.p. 171°, yield 1.1 g. (Found : C, 72.41, H, 5.76; C₁₃H₁₂O₃ requires C, 72.21, H, 5.55%). IR spectra : 3100 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1641 cm⁻¹ (>C=O).

2,9-Dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-furo(3,2-*f*)benzopyran-4-one (Vb) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methylchromone (1g) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (89%, 20 ml) and the solution was heated in a water bath at 80° for 15 minutes. The contents were poured into ice cold water and extracted with ether. It was washed with dil. sodium hydroxide solution and water and the product obtained from ethereal layer was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as cream coloured prisms, m.p. 135°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 72.07; H, 5.60; C₁₃H₁₂O₃ C, 72.21; H, 5.55%).;

2,9-Dimethyl-4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIc) :

2,3-Dihydro-2,9-dimethyl-4H-furo(3,2-f)benzopyran-4-one (0.4 g) was refluxed in diphenyl ether (8 ml) with palladised charcoal (10%, 0.7 g) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described before. The dried residue was purified by elution with petroleum ether-benzene (2:3), through column pecked with silica gel. It was crystallized from ethanol as fine small needles, m.p. 147°, yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 72.93 ; H, 4.64 ; $C_{18}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.89 ; H, 4.67%). UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 228 nm (log e 4.72), 264 nm (log e 4.33), 296 nm (log e 4.37), 325 nm (log e 4.30) ; NMR : δ , 2.51 (s, 3H, C_9 -CH₃), 2.57 (s, 3H, C_9 -CH₃), 6.29 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C_8 -H), 7.01 (s, 1H, C_8 -H), 7.37 (s, 1H, C_8 -H) 7.76 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C_6 -H).

9-Methyl-4H-furo(3,2-f) benzopyran-4-one (VIId) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methylchromone (0.7 g) in ethyl acetate (120 ml) and osmium tetroxide (50 mg) in water (40 ml) were vigorously stirred for 20 minutes. Potassium periodate (1.5 g) was added in small quantities (as in case of VIb). The intermediate 5 acetaldehyde product was treated with PPA (15 ml) for 3 hr at 125°,

and gave VIId (160 mg). It crystallized from ethanol as fine needles, m.p. 140°. (Found : C, 71.86 ; H, 4.09 ; $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.00 ; H, 4.00%). NMR : δ , 2.62 (s, 3H, C_9 -CH₃), 6.35 (d, 1H, J=6Hz, C_8 -H), 7.28 (d, 1H, J=2Hz, C_3 -H) 7.78-7.89 (m, 3H, C_2 -H, C_6 -H and C_8 -H).

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